

A Theoretical Framework on the Role of Human Capital in Fostering Resilience in Tourism SMEs

Cadre théorique sur le rôle du capital humain dans le renforcement de la résilience des PME touristiques

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Date de soumission : 20/06/2025

Date d'acceptation : 02/08/2025

Pour citer cet article :

AHACHMI. M. & LAHFIDI . A. (2025) « A Theoretical Framework on the Role of Human Capital in Fostering Resilience in Tourism SMEs », Revue Française d'Économie et de Gestion « Volume 6 : Numéro 8 » pp : 135- 160.

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Abstract

In the face of disruptions such as pandemics, climate change, and geopolitical tensions, resilience has become essential for tourism SMEs (Duchek, 2020; Linnenluecke & Griffiths, 2012). While research often focuses on structural and operational aspects, the human dimension, especially leadership and social capital, remains less explored (Burnard & Bhamra, 2011; Claridge, 2018). This article proposes a model in which transformational and transactional leadership (Bass, 1985; Avolio & Bass, 1995), along with structural, relational, and cognitive social capital (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998; Coleman, 1990), act as key enablers of resilience.

Grounded in the Resource-Based View (Barney, 1991), dynamic capabilities theory (Teece, 2007), and network theory (Granovetter, 1973; Burt, 1992), the model shows how these human factors help SMEs adapt and recover (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2009). It emphasizes the interplay between leadership and social ties in sustaining continuity and renewal (McManus et al., 2008; Partelow, 2021). This framework informs future research and offers practical tools for managers navigating unstable tourism environments (Rastegar et al., 2023; Suherman et al., 2024).

Keywords : «Organizational resilience»; «Social capital»; «Tourism SMEs»; «Leadership».

Résumé

Dans un contexte marqué par les pandémies, le changement climatique et les tensions géopolitiques, la résilience est devenue cruciale pour les PME touristiques (Duchek, 2020 ; Linnenluecke & Griffiths, 2012). Si la recherche s'intéresse surtout à la résilience structurelle, l'impact du capital social et du leadership reste sous-exploré (Burnard & Bhamra, 2011 ; Claridge, 2018). Cet article propose un modèle mobilisant le leadership transformationnel et transactionnel (Bass, 1985 ; Avolio & Bass, 1995) et les trois formes du capital social (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998 ; Coleman, 1990) comme leviers de résilience.

Ancré dans la RBV, les capacités dynamiques (Teece, 2007) et la théorie des réseaux (Granovetter, 1973 ; Burt, 1992), le modèle montre comment ces facteurs humains permettent aux PME d'absorber les chocs et d'assurer leur continuité (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2009 ; McManus et al., 2008). Il vise à éclairer la recherche future et à fournir aux gestionnaires des clés pour renforcer la résilience en contexte incertain (Rastegar et al., 2023 ; Suherman et al., 2024).

Mots clés : «Résilience organisationnelle » ; «Capital social» ; «PME touristiques»; «Leadership».

Introduction

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are key drivers of economic and social development in both developed and developing countries. In the tourism sector, they significantly contribute to job creation, local value generation, and innovation (Ahachmi, & al, 2024). Their agility and closeness to consumers position them as vital players in enhancing regional competitiveness (Khairy, & al, 2023).

However, SMEs are highly vulnerable to external shocks and systemic crises. Their small size, limited resources, and seasonal dependency increase their exposure to risk, particularly in tourism, a sector prone to disruption (Duchek, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic underscored these weaknesses, highlighting the urgent need for organizational resilience (Lengnick-Hall & Beck, 2005). Without strong financial and structural buffers, survival increasingly relies on their ability to anticipate, adapt, and recover.

To meet these challenges, SMEs are turning to human-centered capabilities that foster resilience. Among them, social capital and leadership are gaining attention. Social capital involves networks of trust, reciprocity, and cooperation (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998; Ahachmi, M., & al, 2024), while leadership refers to the ability to mobilize and align teams around a shared vision (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Both are recognized as key enablers of adaptability and regeneration.

This study examines how the human factor, specifically social capital and leadership, contributes to organizational resilience in tourism SMEs. While each of these dimensions has been studied extensively on its own, their combined influence within this specific context remains insufficiently explored. To address this research gap, we conduct a comprehensive literature review and propose a conceptual framework that integrates both dimensions as strategic enablers of resilience.

The central research question guiding our inquiry is:

How do social capital and leadership interact to enhance organizational resilience in tourism SMEs?

To structure our analysis, we formulate the following supporting research questions:

- ***Q1: What are the conceptual foundations of organizational resilience in tourism SMEs?***
- ***Q2: How are social capital and leadership defined and operationalized within organizations?***
- ***Q3: In what ways do these human-centered factors contribute to strengthening resilience in tourism SMEs?***

Based on a structured literature review from management, organizational theory, and tourism studies, this article introduces a conceptual model emphasizing the human factor's role in building resilience under environmental uncertainty. It is structured as follows: we first define SMEs and discuss theoretical foundations of resilience; then examine social capital and leadership; next, review empirical insights linking these to resilience; and finally propose a conceptual model and related hypotheses.

1. Theoretical background on organizational resilience of SMEs

1.1. What is an SME?

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) are widely acknowledged as a fundamental pillar of economic development and social cohesion. They play a crucial role in job creation, innovation, and local economic dynamism, which explains the increasing attention they receive from governments and institutional stakeholders. However, defining what constitutes an SME remains a complex task, largely due to the multiplicity of legal, economic, and structural criteria, which vary significantly across countries and institutional contexts.

This definitional heterogeneity has led researchers to distinguish between two dominant approaches: qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative approach focuses on socio-economic features such as leadership style, managerial behavior, and informal governance structures, valuable for analytical purposes but difficult to standardize. Conversely, the quantitative approach relies on objective indicators such as the number of employees, turnover, and asset value. Of these, the employee count remains the most frequently used benchmark globally. Nevertheless, thresholds vary significantly across jurisdictions, as illustrated in the comparative classification presented in the table 1 below.

Table 1: Definition of SMEs by employee count in selected countries

Country/Region	Definition (number of employees)
European Union, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland	1–249
Australia	0–199
Canada	0–499
Japan	1–249
United States	1–499
Turkey	1–249

Source: OECD (2010), in (Boumlik, Z., & al., 2021)

Despite the widespread use of such quantitative thresholds, Gibson and Vaart (2008) argue that there is still no global consensus on what precisely constitutes an SME. These criteria, though practical for statistical and regulatory purposes, often lack grounding in macroeconomic

realities and are considered by many researchers as arbitrary (Berisha & Pula, 2015). Consequently, the concept of SME remains flexible and context-dependent, evolving alongside national economic structures and strategic priorities.

1.2. Organizational Resilience

The concept of organizational resilience (OR) has gained prominence at the intersection of management science, organizational psychology, and risk theory, particularly in response to recurrent crises affecting firms in volatile economic, political, or public health environments. Introduced into managerial discourse in the early 2000s, resilience has since evolved into a pivotal analytical lens for understanding how organizations survive, adapt, and transform under conditions of uncertainty and disruption (Lengnick-Hall & Beck, 2005; Duchek, 2020; Ahachmi, M., & al, 2025).

Conceptually, organizational resilience is commonly defined as “the capacity of an organization to anticipate, withstand, absorb, adapt to, and recover from major disruptions” (McManus et al., 2008, Ahachmi, M., & al, 2024). This multidimensional interpretation foregrounds both internal resource mobilization and strategic adaptation. Sutcliffe and Vogus (2003) emphasize that resilience entails more than successful recovery; it involves a learning process and transformative capacity born out of adversity.

Two dominant theoretical perspectives shape contemporary understanding of OR. The dynamic capabilities perspective conceives resilience as a strategic and evolving capability, rooted in the resource-based view (RBV) and shaped by leadership, innovation, and environmental sensing (Teece, 2007; Korber & McNaughton, 2018). In contrast, the processual approach frames resilience as a sequential process, encompassing anticipation, crisis management, adaptation, and learning, that enables continuous organizational reconfiguration over time (Duchek, 2020; Lengnick-Hall et al., 2009; Burnard & Bhamra, 2011).

Recent scholarship seeks to integrate these perspectives into comprehensive frameworks that combine structural, behavioral, cognitive, and temporal dimensions. To illustrate this conceptual evolution, the following table 2 offers a comparative synthesis of key models of organizational resilience, classified by structural form, number of dimensions, and focal components.

Table 2: Comparative Overview of Organizational Resilience Frameworks

Structure Type	Authors	Key Dimensions
Two-factor models	McManus et al. (2008)	Situational awareness, Adaptive capacity
	Lee et al. (2013)	Adaptability, Planning
Three-factor models	Välikangas (2010)	Organizational adaptation, Resources, Learning
	McManus et al. (2007)	Awareness, Vulnerability management, Adaptation
Four-factor models	Vogus et al. (2007)	Robustness, Agility, Integrity, Network capability
Five to factor models	Mallak (1998)	Cognitive, emotional, structural, and relational capacities; Learning; Responsiveness
	Burnard & Bhamra (2011); Linnenluecke et al. (2012)	Weak signal detection, Response, Organizational learning, Regeneration, Proactive anticipation
	Lee, Vargo & Seville (2013)	Adaptability, Planning, Leadership, Innovation, Environmental scanning, Employee engagement

Source : Authors

Nevertheless, these models converge on several critical elements: proactive planning, rapid adaptability, post-crisis learning, and the mobilization of leadership to strengthen cohesion and responsiveness (Ahachmi, M., & al, 2025). Collectively, they offer a robust foundation for guiding organizations, particularly SMEs, toward building sustainable resilience in volatile and uncertain environments.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Social Capital theory

The concept of social capital has attracted sustained scholarly attention in management sciences since the 1990s, particularly as a theoretical lens to explore how embedded social relationships contribute to organizational adaptability and resilience in turbulent environments (Bertolini & Bravo, 2004; Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998). Rooted in the resource-based view (RBV) of the firm (Barney, 1991), which emphasizes the strategic value of unique, rare, and inimitable resources, Social Capital Theory (SCT) complements this perspective by focusing on the intangible relational assets that exist within and beyond organizational boundaries (Ozanne et al., 2022). Social capital, as conceptualized by Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998, p. 243), is defined as “the sum of the actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or a social unit.”

This theoretical foundation highlights two critical components: resources and networks of relationships. These relational structures create the conditions for access to valuable knowledge, cooperation, and support, especially in contexts where formal institutions and market mechanisms are weak or disrupted (Portes, 1998; Zhang & Wong, 2008). In the tourism sector, which is service-based and interaction-intensive, such informal relational mechanisms become even more relevant to ensure resilience, especially among SMEs operating with limited structural resources (Chowdhury et al., 2020).

The development of SCT has been enriched by foundational contributions from multiple disciplines:

- **Pierre Bourdieu (1990)** defined social capital as the aggregate of actual or potential resources linked to possession of a durable network of institutionalized relationships. His work emphasizes the convertibility of social capital into economic and cultural capital, thereby reinforcing social stratification. Social capital, in his view, is unequally distributed and often serves to reproduce existing hierarchies.
- **James Coleman (1988, 1990)** advanced a more functionalist perspective, conceptualizing social capital as a mechanism embedded in social structures that facilitates coordinated action. He highlighted the importance of reciprocity norms, trust, and closed networks for social regulation and collective efficacy.
- **Robert Putnam (2000)** distinguished between bonding social capital (inward-focused ties that reinforce homogeneity and solidarity) and bridging social capital (outward-looking ties connecting diverse groups). He warned that declining civic engagement weakens social cohesion and collective problem-solving capacity, thereby undermining societal resilience.
- **Nan Lin (2001)** proposed a strategic and utilitarian view, positioning social capital as the capacity of individuals or organizations to mobilize resources from their social networks to achieve goals. His model underscores the significance of network structure, accessibility, and intentional use of ties, while acknowledging structural inequalities (homophily and social stratification) that influence access to such capital.

the literature also distinguishes between internal and external social capital (Tsai & Ghoshal, 1998; Inkpen & Tsang, 2005).

- **Internal social capital** refers to the relationships among members within an organization (between employees, departments, or units). It fosters intra-organizational knowledge sharing, cross-functional collaboration, and a unified sense of purpose.

- **External social capital**, on the other hand, encompasses the ties with external stakeholders such as suppliers, customers, and institutional partners. It serves as a bridge to the outside environment, enabling access to new ideas, resources, and markets.

Both types of social capital are essential and often interdependent. Strong internal social capital provides the relational foundation and cognitive alignment necessary to build and sustain high-quality external relationships (Chowdhury et al., 2020; Morrish & Jones, 2020).

To grasp the conceptual depth and interdisciplinary foundation of social capital, it is necessary to examine its seminal definitions. Across sociology, political science, and organizational studies, scholars have articulated diverse understandings of social capital's structure, purpose, and mechanisms. Table 3 presents a synthesis of key theoretical contributions.

Table 3: Key Definitions and Conceptual Dimensions of Social Capital

Authors	Definition	Key Elements
Bourdieu (1986), cited in Bhandari & Yasunobu (2009)	"... The sum of the actual or potential resources that are linked to the possession of a durable network of more or less institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition, in other words, to membership in a group."	- Social network
Coleman (1988), cited in Storberg (2002, p. 484)	"Social capital may be defined operationally as the resources embedded in social networks accessed and used by actors for actions... And social capital can also be envisioned as investment by individuals in interpersonal relationships useful in the markets."	- Reciprocity (including trust) - Information channels - Information flows - Social norms as sanctions
Putnam (1994), cited in Bhandari & Yasunobu (2009)	"... Features of social organization, such as trust, norms, and networks that can improve the efficiency of society by facilitating coordinated actions."	- Interpersonal ties - Social networks - Norms of reciprocity - Social norms
Rancis Fukuyama (cited in Bhandari & Yasunobu, 2009)	"The ability of the people to work together for common purposes in groups and organizations."	- Trust
Lin (2001: 19), cited in Bhandari & Yasunobu (2009)	"... Investment in social relations with expected returns in the marketplace." / "... Resources embedded in social networks accessed and used by actors for actions."	- Social resource - Access to and use of resources
OECD (2001: 41), cited in Bhandari & Yasunobu (2009)	"... Networks together with shared norms, values, and understandings that facilitate cooperation within or among groups."	Networks, values
Robison et al. (2002), cited in Bhandari & Yasunobu (2009)	"... A person's or group's sympathy toward another person or group that may produce a potential benefit, advantage, and preferential treatment for"	- Transformational capacity

Authors	Definition	Key Elements
	<i>another person or group of persons beyond that expected in an exchange relationship.”</i>	
Capital (2000)	<i>“... The institutions, relationships, and norms that shape the quality and quantity of a society’s social interactions. Social capital is not just the sum of the institutions which underpin a society; it is the glue that holds them together.”</i>	Relation, interactions
Bhandari Yasunobu (2009)	<i>“A collective asset in the form of social relations, & shared norms, and trust that facilitate cooperation and collective action for mutual benefits. It is a capital asset produced through...”</i>	Social network - Norms of reciprocity

Source : Authors

❖ Dimensions of Social Capital

Social capital, as conceptualized in contemporary organizational theory, is widely acknowledged as a multidimensional construct. The most influential and widely accepted framework is that of Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), who distinguish between three interrelated dimensions: structural, cognitive, and relational. This tripartite model has since been refined and extended by several scholars (Claridge, 2018; Granovetter, 1992), and serves as a robust analytical foundation for understanding how social ties influence organizational outcomes such as resilience, learning, and performance.

▪ Structural Dimension

The structural dimension of social capital refers to the overall architecture and configuration of the social network in which an individual or organization is embedded. It encompasses the presence and pattern of ties between actors, as well as the roles, rules, and procedures that govern interactions (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998; Claridge, 2018). This dimension is tangible and observable, as it pertains to who interacts with whom, the frequency of interactions, the density of connections, and the centrality or positioning of actors within the network (Davenport & Daellenbach, 2011).

A well-developed structural social capital enables access to valuable information, facilitates the diffusion of knowledge, and supports coordination among actors. For SMEs, strong structural ties can be instrumental in mobilizing external resources quickly during periods of disruption or crisis.

▪ Cognitive Dimension

The cognitive dimension of social capital captures the extent to which actors in a network share common understandings, mental models, and interpretive frameworks. This includes shared

language, narratives, values, and belief systems (Păunescu & Badea, 2014; Claridge, 2018). These elements are essential for effective communication, mutual recognition, and strategic alignment within and across organizational boundaries.

Unlike structural capital, cognitive social capital is less visible but equally critical. It enables actors to develop a collective identity and shared goals, thereby enhancing collaboration, knowledge integration, and decision-making coherence, particularly in contexts characterized by uncertainty and complexity.

▪ **Relational Dimension**

The relational dimension refers to the quality of personal relationships developed through repeated interactions over time. It includes attributes such as trust, mutual respect, obligations, and reciprocity (Coleman, 1990; Claridge, 2018). This dimension reflects the emotional and normative strength of relationships and the extent to which actors are willing to act for the collective good, often beyond contractual or transactional motives.

Relational social capital is particularly valuable in crisis contexts, where rapid coordination and mutual support are required. High levels of trust and commitment reduce uncertainty, foster cooperation, and lower transaction costs, making relational capital a powerful enabler of resilience

❖ **Social capital contribution to the Organisational resilience of SMEs**

Social capital is widely recognized as a key determinant of organizational resilience, especially in the context of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating within the tourism sector. The theoretical foundation of social capital is deeply intertwined with network theory, which offers a relational perspective to analyze how actors interact, share resources, and build trust within formal and informal structures (Granovetter, 1973; Burt, 1986; Coleman, 1990). According to Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), social capital is more than a social construct; it is a dynamic asset rooted in network embeddedness that enhances collective capacity to withstand and adapt to disruptions.

Touristic SMEs, often constrained by limited internal resources, heavily rely on their relational capital, trust-based interactions, community ties, and institutional linkages, to manage uncertainty and respond to crises. Numerous empirical studies have demonstrated that firms with rich social capital, whether through dense local networks, inter-organizational collaboration, or shared cultural norms, are better positioned to recover from external shocks and implement adaptive strategies. These networks enable SMEs to access timely information,

co-develop innovations, share risk, and benefit from mutual aid during disruptions such as natural disasters or pandemics.

The following table 4 synthesizes some studies that illustrate how social capital, serves as a critical lever for resilience in touristic SMEs across various geographic and institutional contexts.

Table 4: Social Capital and Resilience in Tourism SMEs: A Comparative Empirical Overview

Authors	Research Problem	Methodology	Findings
Suherman et al. (2024)	<i>How relational capital, innovation ambidexterity drive resilience in tourism SMEs</i>	& Quantitative survey (132 SMEs, 568 responses); SEM via AMOS	Relational capital, frugal innovation, ambidexterity form mediating pathways from digital transformation to resilience
Rastegar al. (2023)	<i>What crisis resilience et strategies serve tourism SMEs during COVID-19?</i>	Multi-case qualitative study in Iran (2020–22)	Leadership flexibility, stakeholder communication, values-based motivation underpin survival strategies
Ozanne et al. (2022)	<i>How social capital affects dynamic capability and resilience in tourism SMEs</i>	Mixed method evaluating bonding/bridging social capital	Bonding fosters rapid recovery; bridging supports long-term adaptability; social capital positively correlates with resilience
Rastegar, Seyfi & Shahi (2023)	<i>What resilience strategies do tourism SMEs employ during the COVID-19 crisis in developing contexts?</i>	Qualitative multiple case study with interviews (2020–22) in Iranian tourism SMEs	Leadership flexibility, stakeholder communication, and values-based motivation underpin adaptive crisis responses
Partelow (2021)	<i>How does community social capital support disaster resilience in coastal tourism communities?</i>	Case study of post-quake recovery on Gili Trawangan, Indonesia; mixed qualitative & quantitative analysis	High levels of bonding, bridging, and linking capital enabled collective action and self-organized recovery, even where external aid was lacking

Source : Authors

Extant literature on small firm social capital and Organizational Resilience revealed some evidence of positive statistical association , Thus, we assume that:

H1: Social capital has a positive effect on the Organizational Resilience of touristics SMEs

▪ **Relational Social Capital and Organizational Resilience**

Relational social capital refers to the nature and quality of personal relationships developed through interactions, trust, norms, and mutual obligations (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998). In the tourism context, Suherman et al. (2024) show that interpersonal trust and mutual support among

tourism actors foster proactive collaboration, accelerating recovery after shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, Islam et al. (2025), studying Bangladeshi touristic SMEs, highlight that shared trust among partners enabled the rapid deployment of digital services, thus enhancing adaptability and survival during crisis periods.

This evidence reinforces the idea that relational capital, grounded in trust and affective bonds, empowers SMEs to better absorb disruptions and regenerate their operations.

H1.a: Relational social capital is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.

▪ **Structural Social Capital and Organizational Resilience**

Structural social capital encompasses the network configuration: who interacts with whom, how frequently, and through which channels (Burt, 1992; Coleman, 1990). SMEs embedded in dense and diverse networks benefit from greater access to information, knowledge spillovers, and mutual aid. Richards & Hall (2021) demonstrate that network centrality and bridging ties among tourism operators in North America enable collective resource mobilization and faster crisis response.

Thus, SMEs occupying favorable positions in interorganizational networks are more resilient because they benefit from redundant information paths, strong interdependence, and rapid coordination.

H1.b: Structural social capital is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.

▪ **Cognitive Social Capital and Organizational Resilience**

Cognitive social capital refers to shared codes, narratives, and systems of meaning that facilitate mutual understanding and coordinated action (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998). It plays a vital role in tourism SMEs where rapid coordination is essential in times of disruption. Islam et al. (2025) emphasize that shared vision and values among tourism stakeholders facilitated digital transformation during the pandemic, which proved critical to business continuity. Similarly, Hernández-Perlines & López-Flores (2019) show that shared cognitive frameworks support innovation and adaptability in rural tourism firms in Spain.

Cognitive social capital allows actors to interpret threats consistently, align objectives, and act collectively, making it an enabler of both proactive and reactive forms of resilience.

H1.c: Cognitive social capital is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.

2.2. Leadership Theory

Leadership theory has evolved through a dynamic interplay between psychology and management science. Early perspectives, such as Carlyle's "great man" theory (1888), emphasized innate leader traits. Later, the behavioral approach (Lewin, 1935; Blake & Mouton, 1964) focused on leadership styles, autocratic, democratic, and laissez-faire, and the balance between task and people orientation.

The emergence of contingency theories, including Fiedler's LPC model (1967) and Hersey and Blanchard's situational leadership, introduced the idea that leadership effectiveness depends on the fit between style and context, emphasizing adaptability and responsiveness.

Two dominant paradigms, transactional and transformational leadership, shape contemporary theory. Transactional leadership, built on contingent rewards and corrective actions (Bass, 1985; Avolio & Bass, 2004), ensures performance through structure, goals, and rule compliance, making it effective in stable environments but limited in fostering innovation. In contrast, transformational leadership aims to elevate motivation and performance through vision, intellectual stimulation, and individualized support (Bass & Riggio, 2006). This approach enhances commitment and adaptability, especially critical in dynamic settings.

Recent literature increasingly advocates integrated models that blend transactional structure with transformational inspiration, a trend aligned with the concept of resilient leadership. This evolving perspective underscores leadership's strategic role in fostering adaptability and resilience, particularly in volatile sectors like tourism.

To trace this evolution, the following table 5 presents foundational leadership definitions, highlighting the shift from trait-based to context-driven and adaptive leadership frameworks.

Table 5: Leadership Theories and Key Concepts

Authors	Definition	Key Elements
Carlyle (1888)	<i>"Leaders are born, not made. Great men possess innate traits that predestine them to lead."</i>	Innate traits - Personality-based approach
Lewin et al. (1935)	<i>"Leadership styles can be categorized as autocratic, democratic, or laissez-faire, each producing different effects on group performance and morale."</i>	Leadership styles - Behavioral approach
Blake Mouton (1964)	<i>& "Effective leadership balances concern for people with concern for production, represented in a managerial grid."</i>	Task-oriented. people-oriented leadership
Fiedler (1967)	<i>"Leadership effectiveness depends on the match between a leader's style and the favorableness of the situation."</i>	Contingency theory - Leader-situation fit

Authors	Definition	Key Elements
Burns (1978), Bass (1985)	<i>“Transformational leadership is about elevating the motivation and morality of both leader and follower through vision, inspiration, and individual consideration.”</i>	Vision - Inspirational motivation - Individual consideration - Intellectual stimulation
Hersey & Blanchard (1988)	<i>“Leadership effectiveness is dependent on the maturity level of followers. Leaders should adapt their style, telling, selling, participating, delegating, according to the readiness of subordinates.”</i>	Situational leadership - Follower readiness - Adaptive style
Avolio & Bass (1995)	<i>“Transformational leaders inspire followers to transcend their self-interests for the sake of the team or organization, creating meaningful change.”</i>	Idealized influence - Transformational outcomes
Wang et al. (2011)	<i>“Transformational leadership enhances individual and organizational performance through empowerment, innovation, and shared purpose.”</i>	Empowerment - Innovation - Shared purpose
Dartey-Baah (2015)	<i>“An integrated model of leadership combines transactional and transformational styles to achieve both vision and structure in uncertain environments.”</i>	Integrated leadership - Crisis adaptability - Resilient leadership
Leitner (2023)	<i>“Inclusive leadership fosters resilience by empowering employees, enabling shared decision-making, and cultivating a culture of trust and interdependence.”</i>	Inclusion - Empowerment - Organizational culture - Agility

Source : Authors

❖ leadership contribution to the Organisational resilience of SMEs

The literature distinguishes between various leadership styles, notably transformational and transactional, each offering distinct pathways to resilience. Transformational leadership, grounded in vision, individualized support, and inspiration (Bass, 1985), has been empirically linked to enhanced adaptability, innovation, and psychological safety among tourism SMEs. Transactional leadership, while more structure-oriented, contributes through clarity, reward alignment, and operational discipline (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Ahachmi, M., & al (2022).

Table 6 below presents a selection of relevant studies illustrating how leadership behaviors influence resilience dynamics at both the individual (employee) and organizational levels.

Table 6: Leadership and Organizational Resilience in Tourism SMEs: Comparative Insights from Recent Empirical Studies

Authors	Research Problem	Methodology	Key Findings
Prayag, Muskat & Dassanayake (2023)	<i>What leadership behaviors foster employee and organizational resilience during COVID-19 in tourism SMEs?</i>	Mixed methods (surveys and interviews in Lankan SMEs)	Supportive and adaptive leadership behaviors improved both employee psychological well-being and firm-level resilience during crisis.
Zhang, Xie & Huang (2023)	<i>How can resilient leadership be conceptualized and measured in the tourism and hospitality sector?</i>	Qualitative interviews (n=77 leaders, employees) + large-scale survey (n=847)	Identified 7 dimensions of resilient leadership (e.g., recovery orientation, contingency planning) that significantly predict employee resilience and reduced turnover intention.
Rastegar & al (2025)	<i>How do tourism SMEs develop resilience strategies in response to COVID-19 disruptions?</i>	Multiple case studies of Iranian tourism firms (qualitative content analysis)	Leadership flexibility, communication, and values-based motivation were critical to enabling adaptive crisis responses.
Suherman, Sunaryo & Ananda (2024)	<i>How do relational capital, innovation, and leadership drive organizational resilience in Indonesian tourism MSMEs?</i>	Quantitative survey (n=132 SMEs) + SEM (AMOS)	Dynamic leadership behaviors (ambidextrous and innovation-oriented) mediate the relationship between social capital and resilience.
Wang et al. (2021)	<i>How does transformational leadership enhance resilience and innovation across organizational levels?</i>	Meta-analysis of 25 years of empirical studies	Transformational leadership significantly improves individual and organizational resilience, particularly through empowerment, shared purpose, and innovation.

Source : Authors

These empirical findings converge toward a central insight: leadership, whether transformational in its motivational drive or transactional in its operational precision, constitutes a strategic lever for resilience-building in tourism SMEs. From enhancing employee adaptability to supporting structural recovery and innovation, leadership behaviors create the conditions under which small firms can not only withstand crises but also reposition themselves for post-disruption success. Accordingly, we propose the following hypothesis to guide our theoretical model:

H2: Leadership is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.

▪ **Transformational Leadership and Organizational Resilience**

Transformational leadership, defined by vision, intellectual stimulation, and individualized support (Bass, 1985), plays a critical role in enhancing organizational resilience, particularly in the volatile tourism sector. Empirical studies consistently affirm Yu, J., & Xiang, K. (2024) finds a significant positive effect on resilience ($\beta = 0.554, p < 0.001$), while Zhang & Xie (2023) highlight leadership behaviors like improvisation and contingency planning that mitigate staff turnover and build adaptive capacity. Further, research from PLOS One (2022) underscores the mediating role of psychological capital, and SAGE (2022) shows that supportive leadership during COVID-19 in Sri Lanka improved both individual and organizational resilience. These findings emphasize the strategic importance of transformational leadership in guiding tourism SMEs through uncertainty.

H2.a: Transformational leadership is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.

▪ **Transactional Leadership and Organizational Resilience**

Transactional leadership, characterized by contingent rewards and corrective actions (Bass & Avolio, 1994), contributes meaningfully to organizational resilience by fostering structure, clarity, and operational stability. While often considered less visionary than transformational leadership, it remains vital in crisis contexts where procedural compliance and rapid decision-making are required. Empirical studies reinforce this role: Khairy et al. (2023) demonstrate that transactional leadership significantly enhances organizational agility, an essential component of resilience, within Egyptian tourism and hospitality firms, notably through structured goal-setting and trust-building mechanisms. Similarly, findings from PLOS One (2022) and Sustainable CE (2025) indicate that directive leadership supports psychological safety, responsiveness, and employee adaptability during crises. These insights underline the stabilizing power of transactional leadership in tourism SMEs, especially where time-bound operations and external constraints demand disciplined and reliable guidance. Transactional leadership can play a stabilizing and resilience-enhancing role.

H2.b: Transactional leadership is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.

3. Results and Discussions

In the context of tourism SMEs, social capital emerges as a vital intangible asset that enhances organizational resilience amid external shocks and resource limitations. Drawing upon the structural, cognitive, and relational dimensions articulated by Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), the

literature underscores the role of social networks in facilitating access to timely information, mutual support, and collective problem-solving. Empirical evidence confirms that dense inter-organizational ties, shared values, and trust-based relationships enable SMEs to adapt, innovate, and recover more effectively from crises (Lee et al., 2018; Islam et al., 2025). By fostering cooperation and reducing uncertainty, social capital acts as both a buffer and a catalyst, empowering small firms to mobilize resources and capabilities that are otherwise inaccessible through formal mechanisms.

Leadership, particularly transformational and transactional forms, represents a central human lever in cultivating organizational resilience within touristic SMEs. Transformational leadership, grounded in vision, inspiration, and individualized consideration, has been widely recognized for enhancing adaptability, innovation, and psychological safety during periods of disruption (Bass, 1985; Avolio & Bass, 1995). Concurrently, transactional leadership provides operational structure and discipline, facilitating goal alignment and performance monitoring, which are essential under crisis-induced constraints. Empirical studies from diverse geographical contexts, including Sri Lanka, China, and Egypt, confirm that both styles contribute to resilience, albeit through different mechanisms: transformational leadership fosters proactive change, while transactional leadership ensures procedural reliability and responsiveness (Zhang & Xie, 2023; Khairy et al., 2023).

Taken together, social capital and leadership constitute complementary pillars of the human factor in organizational resilience. While social capital enhances relational infrastructure and collective action, leadership shapes strategic direction, mobilizes resources, and sustains morale under pressure. This dual influence is particularly salient in the tourism sector, where SMEs operate in high-uncertainty environments with limited formal buffers. Theoretical and empirical insights suggest that organizations combining high levels of social capital with effective leadership are better positioned not only to withstand crises but also to engage in post-disruption regeneration and strategic repositioning. Hence, resilience-building in touristic SMEs should be conceptualized as a socio-relational and leadership-driven process anchored in human-centered capabilities.

Figure 1 presents the research model linking social capital and leadership to organizational resilience in tourism SMEs. Social capital is divided into structural, relational, and cognitive dimensions (H1a–H1c), while leadership includes transformational and transactional styles (H2a–H2b). The model hypothesizes that these factors positively influence resilience.

Figure 1 :Research model

Source: Authors

Table 7 presents the key variables used in this study, along with their conceptual definitions and corresponding sources from the literature

Table 7: Variable definition

Variable	Definition	Source
Organizational Resilience (OR)	<i>The ability of an organization to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from major disruptions.</i>	McManus et al. (2008); Duchek (2020)
Social Capital (SC)	<i>The sum of actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or organization.</i>	Nahapiet & Ghoshal (1998)
Relational Capital	Social <i>The quality of interpersonal relationships, such as trust, mutual respect, and shared obligations, among members of a network.</i>	Coleman (1990); Claridge (2018)
Structural Capital	Social <i>The overall configuration of the social network, including existing ties, frequency of interaction, and centrality within the network.</i>	Burt (1992); Nahapiet & Ghoshal (1998)
Cognitive Capital	Social <i>The shared values, narratives, codes, and systems of meaning that facilitate mutual understanding among actors.</i>	Păunescu & Badea (2014); Nahapiet & Ghoshal (1998)
Leadership	<i>The ability of an individual to influence, motivate, and guide group or organizational members toward the achievement of common goals.</i>	Bass (1985); Avolio & Bass (1995)
Transformational Leadership	<i>A leadership style that inspires and intellectually stimulates followers, and attends to their individual needs while promoting a shared vision.</i>	Bass & Riggio Burns (2006); (1978)

Variable	Definition	Source
Transactional Leadership	<i>A leadership style based on conditional exchanges, active supervision, rewards, and sanctions aimed at achieving organizational goals.</i>	Bass & Avolio (1994)

Source: Authors

Table 8 outlines the research hypotheses developed from the theoretical framework. Each hypothesis specifies the expected relationship between the explanatory variables, organizational resilience in tourism SMEs.

Table 8: Research hypotheses

Hypothesis	Independent variable	Dependent variable
H1 : <i>Social capital has a positive effect on the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.</i>	Social Capital (SC)	Organizational Resilience (OR)
H1.a : <i>Relational social capital is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.</i>	Relational Social Capital	
H1.b : <i>Structural social capital is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.</i>	Structural Social Capital	
H1.c : <i>Cognitive social capital is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.</i>	Cognitive Social Capital	
H2 : <i>Leadership (transformational and transactional) has a positive effect on the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.</i>	Leadership	
H2.a : <i>Transformational leadership is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.</i>	Transformational Leadership	
H2.b : <i>Transactional leadership is positively associated with the organizational resilience of tourism SMEs.</i>	Transactional Leadership	

Source: Authors

Conclusion

This study explored the human dimensions of organizational resilience in touristic SMEs by focusing on two critical intangible levers: social capital and leadership. Grounded in a robust theoretical framework (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998; Bass & Riggio, 2006) and supported by recent empirical insights (Suherman et al., 2024; Zhang & Xie, 2023; Rastegar et al., 2023), our analysis highlights how these two constructs, relationally and behaviorally embedded, jointly enable small tourism firms to anticipate, withstand, and recover from crises.

In a sector characterized by volatility, seasonality, and structural vulnerability (Berisha & Pula, 2015; Boumlik et al., 2021), social capital emerges as a strategic infrastructure that facilitates access to external resources, promotes trust-based collaboration, and enhances collective

problem-solving capacity (Coleman, 1990; Claridge, 2018). The structural dimension supports inter-organizational ties and information flow (Burt, 1992), while the relational dimension builds trust and mutual commitment (Granovetter, 1973), and the cognitive dimension fosters shared meaning and strategic alignment (Păunescu & Badea, 2014; Hernández-Perlines & López-Flores, 2019). Together, these dimensions help tourism SMEs to remain cohesive and mobilize quickly in times of disruption (Partelow, 2021; Ozanne et al., 2022).

Simultaneously, leadership acts as a catalyst for adaptive change and psychological safety. Transformational leadership, through its emphasis on vision, intellectual stimulation, and individualized support (Bass, 1985; Avolio & Bass, 1995), has been consistently associated with higher levels of resilience, innovation, and post-crisis renewal (Yu & Xiang, 2024; Prayag & Dassanayake, 2023). Transactional leadership, while more focused on structure and control, plays a stabilizing role by ensuring goal clarity, procedural discipline, and accountability, elements particularly crucial in crisis contexts (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Khairy et al., 2023). Empirical research confirms that both styles, though distinct, contribute in complementary ways to resilience-building (Dartey-Baah, 2015; Zhang & Xie, 2023).

Ultimately, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the human-centered drivers of organizational resilience. It underscores that resilience in tourism SMEs is not solely a function of strategic planning or technological capability, but equally, if not more so, a function of relationships and behaviors. These human elements enable SMEs to respond with agility and coherence in the face of adversity, turning social embeddedness and leadership competence into sources of competitive advantage (Teece, 2007; Duchek, 2020).

Future research should further examine the interactive effects of social capital and leadership across various crisis typologies and cultural environments, especially in the Global South. Longitudinal and mixed-method designs could also provide richer insights into how these intangible assets evolve and interact over time to support resilience and regeneration in resource-constrained contexts (Linnenluecke & Griffiths, 2012; Korber & McNaughton, 2018).

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